

**ON COMBATING CRIMES IN THE FIELD OF INFORMATION
TECHNOLOGY**

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As long as crime and organized crime remained domestic issues, the history of international law enforcement and judicial cooperation proceeded at a leisurely pace. Many years passed from when private police officers and private security companies were first used to collect evidence and apprehend offenders abroad, to when the first formal arrangements were made for law enforcement cooperation. Initiatives for formal judicial co-operation arrangements emerged even more slowly. The first modern multilateral treaties on cooperation in criminal matters did not appear until less than fifty years ago.¹

The success of international cooperation depends on the existence of unified national legislation in the field of combating cybercrime, which provides for criminal liability for the commission of cybercrime, and national procedural legislation on cybercrime, which establishes the rules of evidence and rules for the conduct of criminal proceedings.

International cooperation could also be facilitated by the harmonization of bilateral, regional and multilateral legal instruments related to cybercrime. Accession to and ratification of regional and multilateral instruments on combating cybercrime is necessary to make these instruments legally binding.

International cooperation is also facilitated by bilateral, regional and multilateral cybercrime treaties (discussed in Module 3 of the Cybercrime Module Series: Legal Framework and Human Rights), subject to dual criminality (i.e., a clause in the treaties that according to which the alleged act must be considered illegal in the cooperating countries). In the absence of dual criminality and unified laws, “safe havens” are created for cybercrime perpetrators in which cybercrime perpetrators cannot be prosecuted. This was seen in 2000 in the case of the creator and distributor of the computer virus, who could not be prosecuted because at the time of the incident his actions were not considered a crime in his country of residence (the Philippines).²

¹ “International cooperation against transnational organized crime: the practical experience of the European Union” by Matti Joutsen // https://unafei.or.jp/publications/pdf/RS_No59/No59_29VE_Joutsen3.pdf

² Официальные механизмы международного сотрудничества // <https://www.unodc.org/e4j/ru/cybercrime/module-7/key-issues/formal-international-cooperation-mechanisms.html>

However, there are exceptions to the dual criminality requirement. For example, Article 29(3) of the 2001 Council of Europe Computer Crime Convention does not require that the conduct in question be criminalized only when there is a need to “urgently ensure the safety of ... computer data” “which is stored on a computer system located in the territory of that other Party and in relation to which the requesting Party intends, as part of mutual assistance, to make a request for search or similar access, seizure or similar security or disclosure of such data” for the predicate offenses enumerated in this Convention (in Articles 2 to 11). Article 29(4) provides for the right of States to refuse a request for security in cases where, under mutual legal assistance, the condition that the offense be criminalized by both Parties is imposed for offenses not listed in the convention.

Five scenarios for the future of international criminal justice cooperation based on observed trends. The goal is not to map out the currents or tidal changes that may affect international cooperation, nor to speculate on potential future events (political or other) that may disrupt current trends and create entirely new scenarios, but rather to share possible outcomes with readers. Although some of the suggested scenarios can appear preferable, or more probable than others, readers are left to draw their own conclusions in that regard, while recognizing that, to be useful as planning tools, any scenario or vision of the future must be connectable to decisions in the present.³

The five proposed scenarios are distinct but not necessarily incompatible:

1. Together forecasts a situation where states forge the political will and willingness to refashion the existing cooperation mechanisms.
2. Unbound reflects a world in which states increasingly rely on bilateral or regional cooperation frameworks, possibly leading to new cooperation zones.
3. Going alone anticipates states preferentially using unilateral actions to achieve their aim, bypassing existing cooperation mechanisms and agreements.
4. Retreat sees the accelerated use of informal cooperation arrangements or alternatives – to the potential detriment of the rule of law and human rights.
5. Renewal posits that states could be compelled to reimagine the international cooperation regime and undertake radical reform efforts, including establishing a binding arbitration mechanism to resolve bilateral disputes.

Scenarios are narrative descriptions of possible futures based on an analysis of current trends. None of the forecast outcomes – whether grim or

³ Peter J. Scoblic and Philip E. Tetlock, A better crystal ball: The right way to think about the future, *Foreign Affairs*, 99, 6, 10–18.

optimistic – are inevitable, but change has undoubtedly already been seeded. Today, imaginable scenarios are even harder to define because of the various international relations and geopolitical trends currently at play, some converging and others diverging. Nevertheless, reverting to the old order is improbable.

As the next geopolitical era is being shaped, many uncertainties persist, and it is hard to predict where the distribution of power will settle. To the extent that the world order is influenced by the global superpowers, it remains ambiguous which state, if any, will lead the reforms. Those who bide their time, waiting for a return of past arrangements, will be ill-prepared for what lies ahead, and it is likely that their own vulnerability to transnational organized crime will be exacerbated.⁴

European Union (EU) policy seeks to combat organised crime. Whilst operational activities such as prosecuting criminals remain the responsibility of EU Member States, the EU's objective is to assist in fighting organised crime more effectively.⁵

EU action is based on various tools, such as gathering reliable crime statistics and establishing networks for exchanging information and best practices. The EU is assisted by its specialised agencies, such as the European Union Agency for Criminal Justice Cooperation, the European Union Agency for Law Enforcement Cooperation and the European Union Agency for Law Enforcement Training.

The Internal Security Fund for the 2021-2027 period builds on its predecessor and adapts it to new developments, such as the need to intensify the fight against terrorism, serious and organised crime and cybercrime

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⁴ World Economic Forum, *The Global Risks Report*, WEF, Geneva, 2020.

⁵ Fight against organised crime // <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/EN/legal-content/glossary/fight-against-organised-crime.html>

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